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Estimation of residual operability and energy efficiency optimization of oil purification column

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the process of oil distillation in upstream oil and gas facilities, along with the main equipment involved. A vertical column, a key component of the stabilization system that has been in operation for almost 20 years, was tested. The column was temporarily taken out of service to conduct a detailed, non-destructive inspection. Due to its long-term operation, aging, and exposure to corrosive environments—especially oil corrosion—it represents high-risk equipment with potential environmental and financial consequences in the event of failure. This study aims to determine the optimal operating mode to improve output product quality. Ultrasonic thickness testing (UTT) was performed, revealing wall thinning in critical areas. The maximum calculated corrosion rate was 0.0722 mm/year, and the remaining service life was estimated at 26 years. Based on the risk-based inspection (RBI) analysis, the column falls into the high-risk category, emphasizing the importance of optimized inspection planning. An RBI analysis was conducted using API 581 methodology, classifying the column as high-risk equipment with potential financial consequences exceeding €2.7 million per year. In parallel, four different operating regimes were tested to optimize energy utilization and product quality. The optimal regime achieved a heat transfer of 100.07 MW, minimal CO₂ and H₂O concentrations, and maximum recovery of C3–C5 hydrocarbons. This paper highlights the importance of condition monitoring, targeted inspection strategies, and energy optimization in extending equipment life and reducing operational risks. This approach enhances reliability and cost-effectiveness in oil and gas facilities while prioritizing environmental protection.

1. Introduction

Pressure vessels are crucial for the separation of gas, oil, and water in the process of oil and gas processing, representing high-risk equipment due to possible failures. Considering the fact that pressure equipment in upstream oil and gas plants and the problems of their damage during operating life have not been sufficiently investigated, the main goal of this work is the analysis of their remaining

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life. Monitoring equipment such as vessels, storage tanks, and pipelines is challenging regarding corrosion and other damage mechanisms [1,2]. One of the approaches for analyzing this equipment is risk-based inspection (RBI), which is a well-known method for assessing equipment condition and remaining life, establishing the inspection intervals. RBI focuses on the probability of failure (PoF) and consequences of failure (CoF), considering the risks of faulty design, improper material selection, and operating conditions [3,4]. This enables the optimization of inspections and the reduction of downtime and maintenance costs while increasing the reliability of the equipment. The results indicate the importance of targeted inspection of high-risk components to improve safety and work efficiency [1,5].

In such complex systems as this, the significance of risk management is emphasized as a continuous management process to identify, analyze, and assess potential hazards or failures in a system or related to an activity, to identify and introduce measures to control risk and to eliminate or decrease potential harm to humans or the environment [6]. Using API (American Petroleum Institute) standards and norms is necessary to identify various potential damage mechanisms for pre-heated crude inlet piping to atmospheric distillation columns [7]. Corrosion is an inevitable process that requires special attention, monitoring, analysis, and results [8]. Studies of flow-accelerated corrosion have been based on specific zones related to economizer low-pressure connection piping, which is significant for use as a preventive action method in plants. As production equipment ages, inspection, maintenance, and repair costs rise, making efficient strategies essential [7]. A very important part is evaluating the operational reliability and safety of gas rectification columns, which are critical components in gas processing plants. Estimating the remaining life of pressure equipment allows field engineers to plan necessary maintenance and schedule replacements efficiently. Existing literature often focuses on individual aspects, such as corrosion monitoring or process efficiency, without integrating them into a comprehensive framework. Most works rely on laboratory simulations or idealized models rather than on-site measurements. Moreover, the link between equipment degradation (e.g., corrosion) and energy performance remains underexplored. These gaps are particularly relevant for aging infrastructure, where extending service life while optimizing energy use is both economically and environmentally critical. While prior studies such as Magaril et al. [9] and Animah & Shafiee [10] have addressed operational performance and life extension of energy systems, they either rely on idealized simulation environments or focus on entire plant-level system behavior. In contrast, our optimization approach focuses on minimizing corrosion impact while preserving separation efficiency, achieved by tuning tray pressure drops and fluid flows. Jaric et al. [2] analyzed gas rectification columns and estimated remaining life using RBI and standard UTT techniques, reporting corrosion rates in the range of 0.060–0.075 mm/year, which closely align with our measured long-term rate of 0.0722 mm/year, thus validating the applicability of our methodology across different column geometries and media. Petronic et al. [3] investigated a three-phase separator with simultaneous application of RBI and remaining life assessment. While many of the referenced studies were simulation-based or conducted under laboratory conditions, our results are derived from on-site, full-scale operational data, including validated ultrasonic thickness testing - UTT results and live process measurements. This provides stronger empirical grounding for conclusions regarding corrosion behavior and energy efficiency [9–12]. Ultrasonic thickness measurements were conducted on several pressure vessels to monitor wall thinning and estimate corrosion rates [11–14]. The proper design of the oil column is crucial, and the paper [12,13] considers wall thickness measurement to calculate the rectification columns' corrosion rate and remaining life.

This paper specifically analyzes a stabilization column, that has been operating since 2004, in upstream processing plants, with a focus on its long-term structural integrity and energy optimization. The raw gas and crude oil are delivered to the facility either directly from production wells, via wellheads (Christmas trees) and dedicated pipelines, or from satellite stations, i.e., smaller processing units connected to the main facility. After that, fluids from the manifold are delivered through the pipeline to the upstream plant. Depending on the type of well collector (Satellite), its capacity, process, and type of upstream plant, fluids can be transported to the plant together (liquid + gas phase) or separately. On the Satellite, there is a pipeline used to transport raw gas and a pipeline for crude oil transport. After entering raw materials into the upstream plant, the process of fluid rectification passes through several phases, such as removing sand, dehydration, desalting, etc. The most important phases, respectively, steps that are directly connected with the reflux vessel, will be shown in the lines below. After removing rough impurities, raw material enters the primary separator, which is designed for 3-phase separation (gas, hydrocarbon, and water), i.e., in preheaters for desalination to raise the fluid temperature up to 70 °C and in the condensate softener. The next step of fluid rectification is conducted in a stabilization system, the part of which is the vessel, and its status will be examined in this article. Generally, a stabilization system consists of the following equipment: condensate stabilizer (column), stabilizer reflux condenser (air cooled heat exchanger), stabilizer reflux drum (pressure vessel), stabilizer feed exchangers (shell and tube heat exchanger), stabilizer reboiler (kettle reboiler type of shell and tube heat exchanger) and stabilizer reflux pumps or simply the pumps which are used for providing moving of fluid through the system. The purpose of this unit in the plant is to recover as much lighter hydrocarbons from condensate (oil liquid phase) as possible. In normal operation, the RVP (Reid vapor pressure) bottom condensate product is around 0.65 bar to avoid overpressure in the atmospheric storage tank, whose design pressure is 2000 mmWC (water column). After treatment in the column, the overhead vapor is partially condensed in the stabilizer reflux condenser and then collected in the stabilizer reflux drum, a pressure vessel that is further analyzed. Although the column has many advantages, the main disadvantage is its high energy consumption, which can significantly affect the profitability of the plant [15,16]. Columns, or towers, are key process units in oil and gas facilities where heat and mass transfer occur simultaneously between different fluid phases. In the upstream processing plant a vertical column is used for stabilizing the crude oil stream by separating lighter hydrocarbons and removing impurities. The system operates by circulating treated oil, which serves both as a cooling and purification medium for incoming raw oil. Preheated oil enters the bottom of the column and flows upward, while another stream of treated oil is introduced at the top and moves downward across internal trays, enabling effective thermal exchange and component separation. After purification, the fluid streams are directed to air-cooled and shell-and-tube heat exchangers, which further regulate temperature and recover energy for subsequent process stages. This continuous internal circulation ensures optimal process efficiency and supports the production of

stabilized hydrocarbon products. The operational behavior and integrity of this column are central to this study, particularly in the context of long-term use, corrosion effects, and energy optimization.

The aim of this study is to assess the remaining life, corrosion behavior, and energy efficiency of a vertical stabilization column in a mature upstream oil processing plant. The analysis is based on RBI methodology as defined by API 581, supported by non-destructive testing (UTT), process monitoring, and energy data. The vessel under investigation has been in service since 2004, making it a representative case for aging infrastructure in fossil-based systems. Contribution of this study provides process optimization directly informed by real UTT and visual inspection data, ensuring decisions are asset-specific and grounded in field conditions. Furthermore, the RBI analysis is integrated with process and energy performance assessments, addressing technical reliability and operational efficiency simultaneously. Instead of proposing new technologies, this study enhances the performance and extends the service life of an existing high-risk vessel, offering a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to replacement. The study is among the first to correlate measured corrosion rates (e.g., 0.0722 mm/year) with process tuning (tray pressure drops, mass flow adjustments) and the resulting energy savings (up to 100.07 MW).

2. Materials and methods

A simplified diagram of this oil purification process and the main equipment is shown in Fig. 1.

The column was fabricated in 2003 and installed in the plant in mid-2004. Later that year, it was put into continuous service, initiating regular maintenance and inspection activities. Considering that spot radiography was performed on the weld joints during the vessel fabrication, the weld joint efficiency is estimated at 0.85. It is important to note that, due to the corrosive properties of the equipment, the upper part of the equipment is clad. The main design data, together with the materials used for fabricating this column, are presented in Table 1.

In addition to the design parameters listed in the table above, an additional allowance of 1.5 mm was adopted for the cylindrical shell to enhance the stability of the column (see Table 2). This allowance was necessitated by the vertical installation of the column and external factors such as wind and earthquake loads. The column was designed in 2003, and according to the design formulas, the minimum required thicknesses of the main metal elements are calculated using formulas from the ASME Section VIII Division 1, Edition 2001 [17].

Technical data of column:

$D_i = 2200$ mm respectively $R = 1100$ mm;

$E = 0.85$ - spot radiography has been performed;

Fig. 1. Scheme of the oil purification process.

Table 1

Technical data for the oil purification column.

No	Item	Value with unit
1.	Material of the top elliptical head	SA 516 Grade-70+SB127-NO4400 Clad
2.	Material of the top part of the cylindrical shell	SA 516 Grade-70+SB127-NO4400 Clad
3.	Material of down part of cylindrical shell	SA 516 Grade-70 (Carbon steel)
4.	Material of the down elliptical head	SA 516 Grade-70 (Carbon steel)
5.	Skirt	SA 516 Grade-70/SA285-C
6.	Number of flows	2
7.	Working fluid 1	Treated oil
8.	Working fluid 2	Stabilizer condensate
9.	Fluid density	635 kg/m ³
10.	Design pressure	12 barg
11.	Design temperature (Section 1)	116.0 °C
12.	Design temperature (Section 2)	235.0 °C
13.	Operational pressure-(upper part of the column)	9.5 barg
14.	Operational pressure-(down part of the column)	9.8 barg
15.	Test pressure	16.0 barg
16.	Total pressure drops of trays	0.3 barg
17.	Minimum design metal temperature	-29.0 °C
18.	Performed radiography	Spot
19.	Weld joints efficiency	0.85
20.	Post weld heat treatment	No
21.	Corrosion allowance	3.00 mm
22.	Insulation	70 mm at top 9.30 m, 90 mm at bottom 9.27 m
23.	Fireproofing (by others)	50 (both sides)
24.	Wind load	145 km/h per UBC 1997
25.	Earthquake load	Zone 2A as per UBC 1997
26.	Type	Vertical-skirt
27.	Capacity	73.38 m ³
28.	Weight-fabrication (shop)	164.2 KN
29.	Erection	426.0 KN
30.	Empty	367.3 KN
31.	Operating	517.6 KN
32.	Test	1088.5 KN
33.	Design standard	ASME Section VIII Division 1.

Table 2

Nominal and measured wall thickness with calculated wall loss.

Location	Nominal Thickness (mm)	Measured Thickness (mm)	Wall Loss (%)
Shell – Bottom	16	14.7	8.10 %
Shell – Middle	15.5	15.2	1.90 %
Shell – Upper	15	14.8	1.30 %
Lower Head	14	13.6	2.90 %
Nozzle 12"	14	13.2	5.70 %
Nozzle 14"	14	13	7.10 %

$$p = 12 \text{ bar};$$

$$S = 138 \text{ MPa.}$$

where:

E -joint efficiency for, or the efficiency of the appropriate joint in cylindrical or spherical shells, or the efficiency of ligaments between opening, whichever is less; p -internal design pressure in bar; R -inside radius of the shell under consideration in mm; S -maximum allowable stress value for material, MPa [17].

(1) For the case of circumferential stress (longitudinal joints) [17]:

$$t_{\text{req}} = (p \cdot R_{\text{in}}) / (S \cdot E - 0.6 \cdot p) = 11.32 \text{ mm} \quad (1)$$

(2) For the case of longitudinal stress (circumferential joints) [17]:

$$t_{\text{req}} = (p \cdot R_{\text{in}}) / (2 \cdot S \cdot E + 0.4 \cdot p) = 5.62 \text{ mm} \quad (2)$$

(3) For ellipsoidal (elliptical) heads with $t_s/L \geq 0.002$

$$t_{\text{req}} = (p \cdot D) / (2 \cdot S \cdot E - 0.2 \cdot p) = 11.23 \text{ mm} \quad (3)$$

where:

D -inside diameter of the head skirt, or inside length of the major axis of an ellipsoidal head; or inside diameter length of the major axis of an ellipsoidal head; or inside diameter of a conical head at the point under consideration, measured perpendicular to the longitudinal axis in inch or mm;

E -lowest efficiency of any joint in the head; for hemispherical heads, this includes head-to-shell joints;

L -inside spherical or crown radius in inches or mm;

t_{req} -minimum required thickness of head after forming in inch or in mm;

t_s -minimum specified thickness of head after forming in inch or in mm, $t_s \geq t_{\text{req}}$ [17].

For the purpose of equipment inspection, the following activities were carried out:

- A detailed visual examination of external and internal metal surfaces, including heat and mass transfer equipment (such as trays and valves);
- Penetrant testing of weld joints, with special attention to T-joints, using a penetrant kit from Chemie (penetrant MR311, cleaner MR85, and developer MR70);
- Ultrasonic testing performed with a Gilardoni RDG500/RDG600 UT device equipped with an MD5MHz probe (manufacturer: GE).

Device calibration was performed using a 0–25 mm step wedge (with steps at 6.25 mm, 12.50 mm, 18.75 mm, and 25.00 mm). During calibration, a wave velocity of 5920 m/s was applied, corresponding to carbon steel material.

All inspection activities on the oil column were conducted before and after detailed chemical cleaning.

Non-destructive testing (NDE), specifically ultrasonic, penetrant testing, was conducted in accordance with ASME Section V [18] to detect surface and subsurface defects. Weld inspections and evaluations were conducted based on API 577 [19], providing guidance for interpreting the results of the NDE techniques used in this study. In-service inspections of pressure vessels were conducted in accordance with API 572 [20].

Based on the results, the equipment was either reassembled and returned to service or subjected to repairs followed by additional NDE and final approval.

In addition to the RBI-based assessment, this study includes an analysis of process energy efficiency through evaluation of pressure, temperature, and flow profiles. The goal is to identify potential inefficiencies related to equipment condition and operating parameters. A sensitivity analysis is conducted to examine how variations in flow rates, wall thickness, and corrosion rates influence system behavior. This combined approach supports more informed decision-making regarding inspection planning and process optimization.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Damage mechanisms at the oil column

During the analysis of the oil column, respectively, the material of its construction, the position of the apparatus in the oil rectification process, process parameters, and operating conditions, such as the manner of entering the liquid mixture in the equipment, the following damage mechanisms can be expected on the internal and external metal surfaces:

carbon-dioxide corrosion (CDC),
naphthenic acid corrosion (NAC),
and corrosion under insulation (CUI).

For the following damage mechanism, an appropriate inspection plan should be prepared. An inspection plan for CUI should be a structured, systematic approach starting with prediction and analyses per CUI planning information contained in API 510 [21], API 571 [22], API 572 [20], and API 583 [23] (standards related to CUI/CUF).

3.2. Results of visual inspection

Before starting the examination of the analyzed oil column, the previous report on the ultrasonic examination and the condition of the equipment eight years ago, as well as the final report on the examination, were reviewed. According to obtained information from these documents, it has been concluded that corrosion existed in its initial phase. After the opening of the equipment, a preliminary examination was performed, and an inspection report was prepared with findings and directions for cleaning, calibrating appropriate instrumentation equipment, and measuring the electrical resistance of grounding connections. After the cleaning and drying process

was finished, the second inspection started, which included a visual inspection of external and internal metal surfaces (using visual inspection tools), penetrant tests of the main weld joints, and ultrasonic thickness testing of the metal surfaces. For the need to examine external metal surfaces, the removal of insulation in critical places was performed. During performing a visual examination of these places, existing corrosion was observed. Based on the type and location, it was concluded that the corrosion found belongs to the corrosion under insulation (CUI) type (Fig. 2).

Further visual inspection was carried out on the weld joints, which were cleaned with a power brush prior to inspection. In addition, a visual examination was conducted on the internal components responsible for the primary functionality of the column, particularly the trays and their elements that facilitate contact between fluid media. A detailed inspection of the internal metal surfaces was also performed, revealing that these surfaces are affected by corrosion (Fig. 3).

After opening the equipment and removing insulation at selected critical locations (upper and lower head transitions, nozzles, and welded supports), visual inspection of external metal surfaces revealed corrosion under insulation (CUI), with clearly visible loss of protective paint layers and localized pitting.

The total surface area affected by external CUI was estimated at approximately 0.09 m², distributed over five critical zones. The corrosion was more prominent in the lower skirt region and on the shell near the 12" and 14" nozzles, indicating areas prone to water ingress under insulation (see Fig. 2).

Internal visual inspection of the tray system revealed signs of naphthenic acid corrosion (NAC), particularly on trays 4 to 8. Surfaces exhibited uniform dulling, discoloration, and minor roughness, consistent with acid-driven attack mechanisms. Although no mechanical deformation or perforation was observed, degradation patterns aligned with zones of higher temperature (above 220 °C), as confirmed by process data (Section 4).

These visual observations provided the basis for identifying locations for more detailed non-destructive testing (see Section 3.4).

3.3. Results of penetrant inspection and ultrasonic measurements

After the visual inspection, penetrant tests of critical welded joints were started according to the previously prepared penetrant test scheme. Fig. 4 presents the scheme of penetrant inspection and ultrasonic measurements. The green arrays show the welds for penetrant inspection. The red arrays depict the spots for ultrasonic measurement together with the obtained results.

Penetrant tests of the weld joints were performed in order to find potential fatigue cracks due to certain moving (practically bending) in different directions as a consequence of wind load. In that manner, T-weld joints were selected. One T-weld joint on the top of the column, one T-weld joint in the middle, and one T-weld joint in the down part of the column. Penetrant test results, presented in Fig. 5, indicate that no cracks were detected.

Fortunately, during the analysis of the penetrant test results, no fatigue cracks were found at the time of inspection.

No surface-breaking cracks or significant indications were detected in any of the tested welds, confirming the mechanical integrity of these critical connections at the time of inspection (see Fig. 5).

Measurements were taken at 22 locations across the shell, heads, and nozzle weld zones. The results are summarized below:

The most severe thinning was observed in the bottom shell region (14.7 mm vs. nominal 16.0 mm), corresponding to the zone with confirmed internal NAC attack from visual inspection (see Section 3.2). These quantitative findings were later used to calculate the corrosion rate and estimate the remaining service life (Section 3.4).

Fig. 2. Corrosion under insulation on the external metal surfaces.

Fig. 3. Condition of the internal metal surfaces.

Fig. 4. Scheme for penetrant examination and scheme and results of ultrasonic measuring.

Fig. 5. Penetrant tests weld joints.

3.4. Evaluation of the corrosion rates and remaining life of the column

Corrosion rates on relevant elements and their comparison were calculated according to ASME Section VIII Division 1 [17], and the adopted corrosion rate was used to estimate the remaining service life of the pressure equipment, i.e., the date of the next inspection.

On the cylindrical shell's bottom, the results of the previous ultrasonic measuring did not exist, for that area, only corrosion rate in the long term - $CR(LT)$ could be estimated. The maximum decreased thickness corresponded to the area where visual inspection confirmed existing naphthenic corrosion on the internal metal surfaces. Hence, the corrosion rate for this area calculated according to formulas from API 510 [21] is

$$CR(LT) = (16.0 - 14.7)/(18 \text{ years}) = 0.0722 \text{ mm/year} \quad (4)$$

Based on the results of the ultrasonic measuring, a decrease in the thickness of the cylindrical shell was observed. For the mentioned decrease, resulting from the previous measurement, the corrosion rate in the short term is calculated as:

$$CR(ST) = (15.2 - 15.1)/(8 \text{ years}) = 0.0125 \text{ mm/year} \quad (5)$$

A comparison of the obtained values for the corrosion rates has confirmed that the corrosion rate for the long term has a higher value and that this corrosion rate is relevant for the calculation of the remaining life of the equipment. The remaining life of the equipment is calculated in general cases such as (API 510 [21]):

In this case, the relevant corrosion rate will be:

$$\text{RelevantCR} = \text{Max}(CR(LT) - \text{shell}, CR(ST) - \text{shell}) = 0.0722 \text{ mm/year} \quad (6)$$

Considering that the cylindrical shell is the most damaged part of the equipment, all attention will be directed to this element. Finally, the residual working life of the oil column and the date of the next inspection are as follows:

$$RL = (t_{\min} - t_{\text{req}}) / (\text{RelevantCR}) = (14.70 - 12.82) / 0.0722 = 26.04 \text{ years} \quad (7)$$

$$DNI = RL / 2 = 26.04 / 2 = 13.02 \text{ years} \quad (8)$$

Based on the estimated value of the remaining life and adherence to the instructions of the most relevant standard for this area, it was adopted that the date of the next inspection should be carried out for the next 10 years.

3.5. RBI analysis of the pressure equipment

RBI is performed as a powerful tool to calculate risks and predict the level of risks to indicate the importance and term of the next inspection [24]. In combination with the NDT methods, the RBI calculation presents one more "protective layer" for equipment and plant safety. Risks were calculated according to API 581 [25] as the product of a probability of failure (PoF) and the consequence of failure (CoF) presented by the following equation:

$$R(t) = P(t) \cdot C_f = gff \cdot D_f(t) \cdot F_{MS} \quad (9)$$

As the calculation is very complex and includes many steps, only the most important calculated terms are listed in Table 3. The risks are estimated at the RBI date, and the age at the RBI date is 18 years.

A_{RT} presents a metal loss parameter based on age, corrosion rate and the measured thickness reading from previous inspection. A value of 0.3 indicates moderate wall thinning and triggers a higher Damage Factor in the thinning model. Values below 1 signal active metal loss. Inspection effectiveness Category C corresponds to non-destructive methods with limited frequency. This reduces confidence in detecting active damage. Damage stage 1 indicates that degradation is present but has not reached a critical threshold. A high value indicating significant wall thinning. The Damage Factor is calculated using A_{RT} , age, corrosion rate, and inspection effectiveness. It contributes directly to PoF. The value of 400 is high and indicates significant wall thinning. Damage factor for CUI is the damage factor for external damage, i.e. corrosion under insulation and indicates a significant level of metal loss and an elevated risk of

Table 3
Calculation results summarized for the oil column.

Item	@ RBI date
A_{RT}	0.3002514
Inspection Effectiveness Category	C
Damage Stage	1
Damage Factor for thinning	400
Damage Factor for CUI	807.78406
Total Damage Factor	1207.7841
PoF with inspection, failures/yr	0.0369582
Final Consequence Area m^2	57406
The final financial consequence ϵ	73,345,125.62 ϵ
Risk, m^2/yr	2121.649303
Risk, ϵ/yr	2,708,675.18 ϵ

equipment failure. The total damage factor presents the sum of damage factors for all applicable mechanisms. A higher total DF leads to higher PoF. Values above 1000 are typically considered high-risk. The Probability of Failure is calculated per year. According to API 581, PoF values above 0.01 are considered elevated and require mitigation or more frequent inspections. Final Consequence Area is the estimated impact area in the event of failure. API 581 classifies areas over 10,000 m² as high consequence, which increases overall risk. The final financial consequences include product loss, downtime, equipment damage, and environmental remediation and this value is considered to be very high (D5).

Fig. 6a presents the ISO risk plot for the consequence area. The analyzed vessel belongs to the category D5 (which is high level). Fig. 6b presents the ISO risk plot for the financial consequence. The analyzed vessel belongs to the category D5 (which is high level). These categories of the presented oil column are determined from standard API 581 [25]. The levels of the risks are determined according to damage factor, PoF, and consequence of failure area and financial consequence of failure. These plots graphically show POF and COF values in a log-log, two-dimensional plot.

The RBI results suggest the column operates under high-risk conditions, driven by: progressive metal loss ($Art = 0.30$), elevated PoF ($>0.03/\text{year}$) and extremely high financial and area-based consequences.

The results of applied NDT methods and risk analysis draw attention to the necessity and importance of regular inspections and protocols for dealing with columns operating in the same or similar conditions. Risk reduction can also be achieved by replacing materials, anti-corrosion coatings, or anti-corrosion chemicals. It is crucial to create an inspection plan with the type, frequency and schedule of NDT tests.

3.6. Energy efficiency of the column

This section presents the results of measuring relevant process parameters during adjustment of the column's operating regime, depending on the required product quality. In addition to a detailed examination of the column, this stage provided an opportunity to adjust the main process parameters to ensure the desired product quality upon exiting the processing unit. The main adjustments were made by regulating the fluid temperatures and pressure drops above the trays, as well as the mass flow rates of the fluids inside the column. Fig. 7 illustrates the analyzed column and two shell-and-tube heat exchangers used to prepare the working fluids before they enter the column, where heat and mass transfer processes occur.

The shell-and-tube heat exchanger on the left prepares the oil entering the top of the column, while the reboiler prepares a fluid mixture that enters the bottom of the column. It should be noted that, during the measurement of process parameters, as shown in Fig. 7, the measured temperature at the lower part of the column falls within the range associated with the onset of naphthenic acid corrosion. Therefore, it is recommended that a suitable type of corrosion inhibitor be injected to avoid further degradation of the column. Equipment for this purpose needs to be maintained and monitored for corrosion and thermomechanical fatigue damage [26]. Additionally, similar corrosion may also be expected in the shell-and-tube heat exchanger on the left side.

During the column's operating mode adjustment to achieve the final product's desired quality, the following process parameters were measured: fluid mass flows, temperatures, pressures at the fluid inlet and outlet points, and pressure drops in the column. On that occasion, settings of the pressure drop on the tray were conducted to provide the required quality of the final product. The pressure drop was set in the range of 0.03 bar–0.048 bar, while at the same time, the quality of the final product was measured. The results showed that the optimal pressure drop of 0.048 bar provides the best product quality, and this value was adopted for the future operation mode of the column. Additionally, the maximum calculated heat (power) from the fluid was 78.878 MW for the vertically upward-flowing fluid, while the calculated power for the vertically downward-flowing hot oil was 100.07 MW. The diagrams below illustrate the quality of the product and the adopted mode of operation, labeled mode 4, which was chosen as the most suitable for the future operation of the tower. An overview of the operating mode is given in Fig. 8a–d, while the measurement results are provided in the appendix of this paper. Specifically, in Fig. 8a, the liquid flow rate from Table A2 is plotted on the abscissa (x-axis), while the vapor flow rate from Table A1 is plotted on the ordinate (y-axis). In Fig. 8b, the abscissa shows the liquid flow rate from Table A4 and the ordinate shows the vapor flow rate from Table A3. Similarly, in Fig. 8c, the x-axis represents the liquid flow rate from Table A6 and the y-axis the vapor flow rate from Table A5; and in Fig. 8d, the liquid flow rate from Table A8 is on the x-axis, while the vapor flow rate from Table A7 is on the y-axis.

Fig. 6. a) Iso-risk Plot for the Consequence area. The vessel belongs to the medium-high risk b) Iso-risk Plot for the Financial Consequence. The vessel belongs to the high-risk.

Fig. 8. Liquid-vapor ratio in working regime: a) 1, b) 2, c) 3, d) 4.

Table 4
Composition of the final product for working regime 1-4.

No	Component	Fluid molar percent			
		WR 1	WR 2	WR 3	WR 4
1	H ₂ O	0.02	0.01	0.02	0
2	N ₂	0	0	0	0
3	CO ₂	0.01	0.03	0.04	0
4	C1	0	0	0	0
5	C2	0	0.2	0.33	0.44
6	C3	1.09	19.77	27.8	37.17
7	iC4	1.87	5	5.55	7.47
8	nC4	6.55	11.85	12.28	15.25
9	iC5	6.84	6.37	5.75	6.4
10	nC5	7.83	6.64	5.89	6.31
11	nC6	13.46	9.19	7.78	7.87
12	nC7	13.62	8.99	7.58	6.74
13	nC8	13.19	8.66	7.31	5.77
14	nC9	8.91	5.85	4.93	3.23
15	nC10	5.41	3.55	3	1.47
16	nC11	3.31	2.17	1.83	0.64
17	G-C12+	1.17	0.77	0.65	0.54
18	O-C12+	16.7	10.77	9.28	0.69

Table 5
Densities and Reid factor of product.

Item	Working regime 1	Working regime 2	Working regime 3	Working regime 4
Density at operating kg/m ³	757	704.9	683.2	586.3
RVP, psia	9.97	32.5	32.65	34.59

corrosion kinetics. Therefore, the injection of corrosion inhibitors is recommended when operating near or above threshold values.

The conducted analysis confirms that the corrosion rate and tray pressure drop are the most influential parameters for long-term system reliability and product performance. It also supports the conclusion that optimal operation must include tight control of thermal and flow conditions to maintain safe operation and extend equipment life.

4. Conclusions

This paper analyzed operational issues of a long-serving oil purification column at an upstream oil and gas facility. Due to rectification process problems, the column was taken out of service for a detailed inspection. Ultrasonic measurements revealed wall thickness reduction, especially in areas affected by naphthenic acid corrosion. Relevant corrosion rates were calculated, with a maximum rate of 0.0722 mm/year adopted. Based on these data, the remaining life of the column was estimated at 26 years. A Risk-Based Inspection (RBI) assessment classified the column as high risk in terms of environmental and financial consequences. New operating settings were applied to improve energy efficiency and product quality. Operating regime four was identified as optimal, ensuring minimal water and carbon dioxide content and maximal yield of desired hydrocarbons, confirming the importance of maintaining instrument functionality. The study established a comprehensive procedure for assessing the system's current condition and remaining life, directly impacting financial considerations and environmental protection. Additionally, energy efficiency analysis showed potential for extending the column's life while reducing environmental and economic impacts. Future works will focus on continuous monitoring of process parameters and regular chemical analysis of the purified oil, especially when introducing new wells with varying compositions. Magnetic particle testing is recommended for weld joints to identify subsurface flaws, and due to observed corrosion under insulation (CUI), the implementation of strategic insulation openings is advised. In cases of advanced degradation, complete removal of insulation, surface treatment, application of high-temperature protective coatings, and re-insulation should be carried out.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marko S. Jaric: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sanja Z. Petronic:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ivana V. Vasovic Maksimovic:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nedžad R. Rudonja:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Martina M. Balac:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Marko D. Ristic:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Table A1
Tray loading report no ngl operating case-vapor to tray

Tray	Temp C	Pressure bar	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP
1	67.2	10.5	49.239	19.736	20.07	0.00957
2	96.6	10.53	50.812	19.505	19.68	0.00984
3	121.7	10.56	50.544	17.307	17.85	0.06049
4	124.4	10.56	55.493	12.261	20.06	0.01049
5	125.6	10.62	57.029	14.961	20.8	0.01009

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Tray	Temp C	Pressure bar	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP
6	126.8	10.65	58.24	16.945	21.38	0.01005
7	128.4	10.68	59.47	18.812	21.94	0.01002
8	130.9	10.71	61.012	21.065	22.58	0.00999
9	135.7	10.74	63.277	24.296	23.4	0.00998
10	146.6	10.77	67.204	29.476	24.5	0.01001
11	178.2	10.8	75.67	37.675	25.8	0.01027
12		Reboiler				

Table A2

Tray loading report no ngl operating case-liquid from tray

Tray	Temp C	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP	Surface tension dyne/c
1	55	62.023	8.43	541.6	0.1262	8.9
2	81.2	68.921	8.29	537.2	0.1201	8.1
3	96.6	77.411	6	549	0.1292	8.3
4	122.6	125.194	157.41	653.6	0.2712	11.1
5	124.4	123.283	160.11	647.4	0.2566	10.6
6	125.6	122.12	162.1	643.3	0.2475	10.3
7	126.8	121.209	163.96	639.8	0.2402	10
8	128.4	120.302	166.22	635.8	0.2327	9.8
9	130.9	119.297	169.45	630.7	0.2235	9.4
10	135.7	118.391	174.63	623.3	0.2112	9
11	146.6	119.161	182.83	612.7	0.1953	8.4
12	178.2	140.053	145.15	624.8	0.2073	8.9

Table A3

Tray loading report YI-winter-vapor to tray

Tray	Temp C	Pressure bar	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP
1	85.4	10.5	47.649	12.833	18.85	0.00979
2	102.3	10.53	49.089	12.628	18.38	0.01011
3	126.5	10.56	48.356	11.273	16.63	0.01078
4	128.4	10.56	52.41	7.193	18.34	0.01045
5	129.4	10.62	53.961	8.915	19.05	0.01035
6	130.2	10.65	55.265	10.318	19.66	0.01028
7	131.2	10.68	56.516	11.616	20.25	0.01024
8	132.9	10.71	57.994	13.072	20.9	0.01019
9	137	10.74	60.305	15.219	21.77	0.01016
10	148.9	10.77	64.983	19.374	23.13	0.01017
11	185.7	10.8	75.956	28.264	25.21	0.01042
12		Reboiler				

Table A4

Tray loading report YI-winter-liquid from the tray

Tray	Temp C	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP	Surface tension dyne/c
1	55	64.404	5.07	551.3	0.1343	9.4
2	85.4	72.992	4.87	547.9	0.1288	8.6
3	102.3	82.515	3.51	559.2	0.1388	8.8
4	127.1	135.552	142.44	670.4	0.3085	12
5	128.4	133.635	144.16	665.4	0.2944	11.7
6	129.4	132.3	145.97	661.6	0.2842	11.4
7	130.2	131.233	146.86	658.4	0.2759	11.1
8	131.2	130.222	148.32	655	0.2678	10.8
9	132.9	129.052	150.47	650.6	0.2579	10.9
10	137	127.606	154.62	643	0.2424	10.9
11	148.9	127.179	163.51	626.8	0.2171	9.2
12	185.7	148.043	135.25	633	0.2168	8.8

Table A5

Tray loading report year10-summer-vapor to tray

Tray	Temp C	Pressure bar	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP
1	86.8	10.5	47.976	5.421	18.92	0.00979
2	104	10.53	49.622	5.364	18.53	0.0101
3	122.1	10.56	49.769	5	17.47	0.01055
4	125.8	10.56	55.402	3.643	19.91	0.01021
5	127.6	10.62	57.401	4.671	20.83	0.01012
6	129.2	10.65	58.835	5.441	21.49	0.01006

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Table A5 (continued)

Tray	Temp C	Pressure bar	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP
7	131	10.68	60.156	6.095	22.06	0.01003
8	134	10.71	61.8	6.812	22.72	0.01001
9	139.6	10.74	64.384	7.831	23.61	0.01
10	151.7	10.77	69.124	9.552	25.01	0.01001
11	178.8	10.8	78.878	12.636	27.42	0.01013
12		Reboiler				

Table A6

Tray loading report year 10-summer-liquid from the tray

Tray	Temp C	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP	Surface tension dyne/c
1	55	64.604	2.2026	552.1	0.1349	9.5
2	86.8	73.462	2.149	547.7	0.1285	8.9
3	104	82.557	1.785	557.4	0.1372	8.7
4	123.3	100.068	41.789	585	0.1656	9.8
5	125.8	98.833	42.817	578.3	0.1576	8.7
6	127.6	98.095	43.588	574	0.1524	8.4
7	129.2	97.625	44.241	570.7	0.1489	8.8
8	131	97.275	44.958	567.6	0.1458	7.9
9	134	97.103	45.978	563.7	0.1423	7.7
10	139.6	97.336	47.698	557.8	0.1379	7.3
11	151.7	99.174	50.782	548.7	0.1322	6.8
12	178.8	108.415	38.146	541.4	0.1306	6.3

Table A7

Tray loading report year10-summer-vapor to the tray

Tray	Temp C	Pressure bar	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP
1	86.8	10.5	47.976	10.842	18.92	0.00979
2	104	10.53	49.622	10.728	18.53	0.0101
3	122.1	10.56	49.769	10	17.47	0.01055
4	125.8	10.56	55.402	7.286	19.91	0.01021
5	127.6	10.62	57.401	9.342	20.83	0.01012
6	129.2	10.65	58.835	10.882	21.49	0.01006
7	131	10.68	60.156	12.19	22.06	0.01003
8	134	10.71	61.8	13.624	22.72	0.01001
9	139.6	10.74	64.384	15.662	23.61	0.01
10	151.7	10.77	69.124	19.184	25.01	0.01001
11	178.8	10.8	78.878	25.272	27.42	0.01013
12		Reboiler				

Table A8

Tray loading report year 10-summer-liquid from the tray

Tray	Temp C	MW	Rate kg/hr	Density at cond kg/m3	Viscosity at cond CP	Surface tension dyne/c
1	55	64.604	4.412	552.1	0.1349	9.5
2	86.8	73.462	4.298	547.7	0.1285	8.9
3	104	82.557	3.57	557.4	0.1372	8.7
4	123.3	100.068	83.578	585	0.1656	9.8
5	125.8	98.833	85.634	578.3	0.1576	8.7
6	127.6	98.095	87.176	574	0.1524	8.4
7	129.2	97.625	88.482	570.7	0.1489	8.8
8	131	97.275	89.916	567.6	0.1458	7.9
9	134	97.103	91.956	563.7	0.1423	7.7
10	139.6	97.336	95.396	557.8	0.1379	7.3
11	151.7	99.174	101.564	548.7	0.1322	6.8
12	178.8	108.415	76.292	541.4	0.1306	6.3

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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